

A questionable catalogue

Luca BIANCHINI ^a and Anna TROMBETTA ^b

^a *Dottore in Musicologia, Università di Pavia, Dipartimento di Musicologia e Beni Culturali*

Cremona, ITALY

^b *Dottore in Musicologia, Università di Pavia, Dipartimento di Musicologia e Beni Culturali*

Cremona, ITALY

luca.bianchini61@gmail.com, anna.trombetta3@gmail.com

Abstract. This paper presents an in-depth investigation into the alleged personal catalogue attributed to Wolfgang Amadé Mozart, covering the period from 1784 to 1791, according to the testimony of Constanze, Mozart's wife. Curiously, neither Mozart nor his relatives or contemporaries ever mentioned it, leaving its authenticity unexamined and unquestioned until now. In this study, we meticulously scrutinise the catalogue, uncovering historical and musical inconsistencies that cast doubts on its origins. Incongruities in dates, handwriting, and watermark usage raise suspicions of a potential 18th-century forgery, challenging the document's credibility and the period of its creation. We wanted to critically evaluate this controversial catalogue, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of Mozart's life and compositions within the broader context of his era.

Keywords: W.A. Mozart, manuscript authentication, document examination, clef analysis, image analysis, signature analysis

1. Introduction.

Constanze Mozart was the first witness to testify to the existence of Mozart's personal catalogue. She claimed that Mozart maintained a record of his works, but interestingly, Mozart never mentioned it during his lifetime, nor did any of his relatives or friends. Constanze's credibility as a source was questioned several times. In 1798, the editor of the Leipzig Allgemeiner litterarischer Anzeiger accused her of fraud and sullyng Mozart's legacy by attributing compositions by other composers to him [1].

The catalogue was vital in organising Mozart's works, many of which lacked signatures and dates. It served as a musical diary, listing 145 pieces composed between 1784 and 1791, providing descriptions and musical incipits to authenticate the compositions. Mozart purportedly would have recorded his works in the catalogue as he completed them. However, the primary significance of the catalogue lies in its instrumental role in assisting Constanze during 1798, as she sought to establish the authenticity of Mozart's unsigned and undated works to facilitate their sale to publishers.

Mozart began writing his catalogue on February 9, 1784, using a small notebook titled 'Verzeichnüss aller meiner Werke.' Today, this catalogue is housed in the British Library in London [2].

During the authors' investigation, they made an intriguing discovery related to the catalogue's cover, which bears Mozart's signature. They found a dubious signature that someone wrote on a sheet of paper attached to a letter from Mozart dated September 29, 1787. This signature, written after Mozart's death, resembles the one on the catalogue cover. It has been traced multiple times in pencil, possibly indicating its use for handwritten proofs. Figure 1 depicts the catalogue cover signature, the authenticated signature from the marriage contract for comparison [3], and the spurious signature on the attached sheet.

Catalogue (1784)

Marriage contract (1782)

Sheet (BD 1067) [4]

Figure 1

2. Analysis

The catalogue presents a multitude of issues and discrepancies. André, the publisher Constanze corresponded with in the late 18th century to sell Mozart's autographs, had already noted the absence of certain pieces listed in the catalogue [5]. Notable differences in tempo, measures, notation, dynamics, instruments, ligatures, and staccato markings exist between the catalogue and Mozart's autograph manuscripts [6]. Additionally, several catalogue entries contain dates incompatible with established biographical facts about Mozart [6, 7].

A peculiar error occurs on sheet 24v, dated December 1790. The entry 'Ein Stück für ein Orgelwerk in einer uhr' (A piece for a clock organ) was mistakenly duplicated on sheet 25v between February 12 and 28, 1791 and then erased. This erasure is a typical copyist's error. Significantly, 'Ein Stück für' appears only on sheet 24v (Figure 2).

Catalogue, 24v (1790)

25v (1791)

Figure 2

The duplicate entry's erasure from sheet 25v was not noted in Alan Tyson's catalogue edition [8], but it is crucial because it questions the authenticity of the catalogue. The catalogue paper only shares a watermark with a letter from 1802 [8], which could imply that the paper was produced around 1800. The absence of the same watermark in other Mozart documents and the lack of use by contemporary musicians or general writers demonstrates the possibility that the catalogue was written in the last decade of the 18th century.

2.1 Methods

The authors employed a graphic forensic analysis to address the catalogue's issues, revealing significant complexities. To comprehensively tackle these challenges, they developed a dedicated C# software designed explicitly for systematic catalogue analysis. The software encompasses a database of Mozart's manuscript characters and signs, serving as a reference for comparison with the catalogue. It evaluates differences in text and music notation, employing a scientific and systematic approach facilitated by computer analysis, ensuring precision and efficiency.

The software comprises three key components: an editor for data entry, a database manager with search functionalities, and a module for character measurement, slope calculation, curvature assessment, and comparison operations. Without the aid of the software, storing images of even a few sentences would entail days of manual work. In contrast, the software can automatically generate an image of a word per second, independently calculating the individual characters. Instead of producing separate images for each word or musical sign, the software employs a single high-definition image for each letter of Mozart and each autograph manuscript. For each word, the software stores in strings the x and y coordinates of the word and the individual coordinates of the characters. Additionally, the software records the coordinates of notable graphical features of each character or musical sign in real-time, enabling the determination of word slopes and their positions relative to margins.

To handle the vast amount of data, the authors created a language with a .gqp extension and a new protocol for distinguishing the characteristics of musical and alphabetical signs. Each data element for individual words or letters is separated by special characters, facilitating real-time reconstruction using C# split functions that produce arrays. Recursive functions are employed to evaluate the data. The program also can differentiate between reference alphabets, distinguishing whether a word is written in the Kurrentschrift taught in Salzburg around 1780 or in the Latin cursive [9]. It can store up to 100 points for each character, on which the program performs calculations necessary for detecting potential forgeries. Users can run multiple program instances simultaneously, enabling immediate visual comparisons. The advanced search function can retrieve various types of textual or musical data. Operations that would take years to perform manually can now be completed in fractions of a second.

The software has archived Mozart's written correspondence from 1784 to 1791, as well as individual words and musical symbols found in the catalogue, music scores, and autograph manuscripts (Figure 3).

The software possesses the capability to store one formatted image per second.

The software can measure and compare the significant graphic points within the manuscript.

Figure 3

2.2 Handwriting.

The study of Mozart's handwriting has received limited attention in scholarly research. Only a handful of pioneering articles have delved into the psychological characteristics of Wolfgang Amadé Mozart and his father through the analysis of their handwriting. Previous studies by Wolfgang Plath concerning Mozart's handwriting lack scientific standards and suffer from self-referentiality due to the predetermined selection of Mozart's autographs, undermining the research's validity [10, 11]. The absence of a comprehensive handwriting analysis of Mozart has contributed to the prevalence of forgeries. In contrast, the computer-based approach adopted in this study maintains objectivity and adheres to the protocol employed in ENFSI's handwriting examination methods [12]. The software's comparison of Mozart's letters written in the same year and the catalogue entries identified a consistent set of words present in both the catalogue and Mozart's correspondence. Each word underwent measurement for parameters such as height, width, slant, proportions, and eyelets. This comparative analysis revealed fundamental discrepancies between the words in the catalogue and Mozart's letters from the corresponding years. Differences could manifest in the characters' height, shape, or alignment. These variations contribute to the overall dissimilarity between the two versions and suggest the involvement of different individuals or variations in writing styles, as demonstrated by comparing data stored in the database. In Figure 4, the catalogue entries are displayed in the first row, while the second row shows the letters sent by Mozart.

Figure 4

In the following analysis, we examine the rendering of the word 'Bassi' in Mozart's manuscripts from the relevant years and compare it to its appearance in the catalogue (Figure 5).

Figure 5

Recurring and almost automatic familiar signs, often sketched without much deliberation, are also present in the music and play a significant role in identifying Mozart's handwriting. The shapes of musical clefs, particularly G, C, and F, are of great significance in the study of Mozart's catalogue. To thoroughly understand these clefs, it is essential to accurately identify the starting and ending points of the line graphics, enabling detailed structural analysis. The use of a computer is indispensable in this task. Scholars can obtain valuable information about the author's handwriting by measuring the horizontal dimensions of the loops and the spacing between each clef and alteration marks (such as flats or sharps). The computer adopts the average distance between the lines of the relative staff in the catalogue or autograph manuscripts as the unit of measurement. The authors have compiled a comprehensive database containing data on the musical clefs in the catalogue and Mozart's autograph manuscripts. Any irregularities or discrepancies can be identified and evaluated through this systematic process. Table 1 provides an example of the average values computed by the computer for the G clefs in the 1785 catalogue compared to Mozart's autograph quartet K.465 (1785). If the catalogue is authentic, these values should be similar. However, substantial differences indicate significant disparities between the two sources.

Table 1

	Distance from the left margin	Distance from the first line	Width	Height	Distance between intersection points	Eyelet	Number of strokes
Catalogue	1.7	0.12	1.6	2.9	1.9	0.2	2 or 1
K.465	-0.4	-0.2	1.5	4.1	2.1	0.3	Only 1

In Figure 6, we can observe the representation of the violin and bass clefs as they appear in the catalogue, followed by the depiction of the violin and bass clefs found in Mozart's manuscripts stored within the database.

Figure 6

The size discrepancy between the clefs in the catalogue and the original manuscripts is notable, particularly considering they were purportedly written in the same month. Additionally, the computer-based analysis examines the ink characteristics, including hue, intensity, and variations. It also evaluates pen pressure and ink concentration, allowing for inferences about writing dynamics. Interestingly, the ink colour of the catalogue entries consistently differs from that of the musical manuscripts from the same month, as the software finds no matches. This difference raises doubts about the authenticity of the catalogue, especially considering the identical pen and ink used throughout. In contrast, Mozart's letters exhibit monthly variations in ink colour. Furthermore, there are discernible differences in musical notations between Mozart's manuscripts and the catalogue. The writing style in the catalogue displays deliberate and uneven movements, with strokes flickering and appearing interrupted. These characteristics create artificial handwriting that tries to imitate an original model. Hesitant pauses, initial and final thickening, slowed movements, and contour distortions result from decreased speed and detached execution. Moreover, wrist inclination and position changes lead to increased pressure while writing (Figure 7).

Figure 7

These factors deviate from the expected consistency with the reference model and contribute to the overall inconsistencies observed in the catalogue.

3. Conclusion.

The personal catalogue attributed to Mozart, documenting his musical output between 1784 and 1791, received authentication from his wife Constanze following Mozart's passing. Constanze is the sole witness to the existence of the catalogue, as no other individuals mention it during Mozart's lifetime. However, scholars have widely accepted this catalogue as a reliable primary source without systematically examining its authenticity.

The authors of this paper conducted a thorough investigation by comparing Mozart's letters and music manuscripts with the catalogue. They developed a new C# software capable of analysing and comparing lexical and musical elements in the autographs, Mozart's correspondence, and Verzeichnüss. This software represents a significant advancement in analysing and comparing the catalogue with Mozart's authentic works. Its comprehensive capabilities, efficiency, and speed enable the examination of vast amounts of data, facilitating the detection of potential forgeries and providing invaluable insights into the authenticity of Mozart's compositions. The program utilises specific reference alphabets derived from late 18th-century manuscripts, which aligns with the period of the catalogue's claimed origin.

Initial findings raise significant doubts regarding the authenticity of the catalogue. They reveal discrepancies in dates, spellings, and information within the Verzeichnüss and suggest the possibility that this notebook was manufactured after Mozart's death, potentially making it a forgery originating in the last decade of the 18th century.

References

- [1] Deutsch, O. E. (1961). *Mozart / Die Dokumente seines Lebens*, Deutscher Verlag für Musik, Leipzig.
- [2] British Library. (n.d.). Mozart's Verzeichnüss. Zweig MS 63.
Retrieved from: https://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Zweig_MS_63
- [3] British Library. (n.d.). Mozart's marriage contract (1782). Zweig MS 69.
Retrieved from: <https://www.bl.uk/collection-items/mozarts-marriage-contract>
- [4] Bauer, W. A., & Deutsch, O. H. (1966-1975). *Mozart / Briefe und / Aufzeichnungen/ Gesamtausgabe / Herausgegeben von der Internationalen Stiftung / Mozarteum Salzburg*. Bärenreiter, Kassel.
(BD is an abbreviation for the comprehensive catalogue of Mozart's letters)
- [5] André, A. (1805). *Thematisches Verzeichniß / sämtlicher Compositionen / von / W. A. Mozart, / so wie er solches vom 9ten Februar 1784 an, bis zum / 15ten November 1791 eigenhändig niedergeschrieben hat / Nach dem Original-Manuscripte herausgegeben / von A. André, Johann André, Offenbach*.
- [6] Bianchini, L., & Trombetta, A. (2018). *Mozart / La costruzione di un genio*. Youcanprint, Lecce.
- [7] Leeson, D. N., & Whitwell, D. (1973). *Mozart's Thematic Catalogue*. The Musical Times Publications Ltd, London.
- [8] Rosenthal, A., & Tyson, A. (1990). *Mozart's Thematic Catalogue: A facsimile*. Cornell University Press, New York.
- [9] Stäps, C. W. H. (1785). *Grundfässe zur Schönschreibekunst*. Carl Wendler, Leipzig.
- [10] Plath, W. (1960-1961). *Die Handschrift Leopold Mozarts*. Mozart-Jahrbuch, Mozarteum, Salzburg.
- [11] Plath, W. (1976-1977). *Beiträge zur Mozart-Autographie II. Schriftchronologie 1770-1780*. Mozart-Jahrbuch, Salzburg.
- [12] European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (2023). *Best Practice Manuals*.
Retrieved from: <http://enfsi.eu/documents/best-practice-manuals/>